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ROLE OF E-TAILING IN BOOSTING THE INDIAN HANDICRAFT INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

Handicraft market in India is growing at a very steady pace. Industry experts believe that global trade now depends upon more on e-commerce along with traditional medium for trading. India is one of the most sought after destinations for handicraft due to variation in culture and people who produce varied kinds of handicraft. Different places in India are famous for different handicrafts like Saharanpur for its wooden articles, the North Western state of Rajasthan for Jaipuri quilts, Gujarat for embroidered stuff, Narsapur for lace and lace material, Punjab for Phulkari, Jodhpur for wrought iron product, etc.

Handicraft industry is one of the biggest employers in rural India. Near about 13 million artisans mostly women and people from weaker sections of the society get job in this industry. Many artisans work on full time and many on part time basis to produce these goods with hands. Low initial investment, potential for export and foreign earning are few factors that are helping this industry to grow further. But Indian handicraft industry is highly decentralized. Rising demand of Indian handicrafts in US, Britain, Canada, Germany, Italy etc provide great opportunity. Each industry need handicraft such as fashion industry, real estate, home décor etc.

For tech savvy buyers online is the easiest way to find and shop for various handicrafts. Also ecommerce is one of the most promising channels in today's marketing scenario for selling handicrafts. It ensures easy availability of goods globally. This paper tries to assess the current scenario, as well as challenges and future prospects of e-tailing for the Indian handicraft industry.

Introduction

Handicraft reflects the culture and skill of local population and hence the country. India is one of the most sought after destinations for handicraft due to variation in culture and people who produce varied kinds of handicraft. Different places in India are famous for different

handicrafts like Saharanpur for its wooden articles, the North Western state of Rajasthan for Jaipuri quilts, Gujarat for embroidered stuff, Narsapur for lace and lace material, Punjab for Phulkari, Jodhpur for wrought iron product etc. Handicraft industry is one of the biggest employers in rural India (Liebl, Maureen and Roy, Tirthankar, 2003). Approx 13 million artisans mostly women and people from weaker sections of the society get job in this industry (Prajapati and Laila, 1981). Many artisans work on full time and many on part time basis to produce these goods with hands. Low initial investment, potential for export and foreign earning are few of the factors that are helping this industry to grow further (Thaimani, K. K, 1987). But Indian handicraft industry is highly decentralized.

“Handicrafts can be defined as products that are produced either completely by hand or with the help of tools. Mechanical tools may be used as long as the direct manual contribution of the artisan remains the most substantial component of the finished product. Handicrafts are made from raw materials and can be produced in unlimited numbers. Such products can be utilitarian, aesthetic, artistic, creative, culturally attached, decorative, functional, traditional, religiously and socially symbolic and significant.” (UNESCO/ITC, 1997)

Handicraft market in India is growing at a very steady pace. It is almost doubling in every five years. In the handmade products India enjoys 2% of share at global level. Because of weak market forces and fake products approx 7 out of 10 people leave this job to explore other opportunities. The Export Promotion Council for Handicrafts (EPCH) handles handicraft export promotion in India. Industry experts believe that global trade now depends more on ecommerce along with traditional medium for trading.

What is e-tailing?

E-tailing or E-retailing refers to the selling of retail goods electronically over the Internet. The term is a short form for "electronic retailing", and surfaced in the 1990s for being frequently used over the Internet (Levy, M., Weitz, B. A., Pandit, A., 2008).

Though there is no standard definition of e-tailing but the OECD (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development) defines e-tailing transactions – “the sale or purchase of goods or services, whether between businesses, households, individuals, governments, and other public or private organizations, conducted over computer-mediated networks. The goods and services are ordered over those networks, but the payment and the ultimate delivery of the good or service may be conducted on or off-line.”

E-tailing or Electronic retailing is a retail format in which the retailers communicate with customers and offer handmade products for sale over the Internet (Mukherjee, A., 2011). E-tailing of handicraft is useful as handicraft sector in India is decentralized and it has vast untapped potential. E-tailing of handicraft also make available the handmade products in the reach of customers of different region. Customers can select wide variety of regional handicrafts through e-tailing. While the Internet continues to provide opportunities for entrepreneurs in the retail industry, it is now primarily used by traditional artisanal retailers as a tool to complement their store and catalog offerings, grow their revenues, and provide more value for their customers.

India is one of the largest users of Internet across the world and expected to cross United States in the coming years (Taylor, T. & Owusu, E.D.E., 2012). Hence e-tailing has huge hidden and untapped opportunities for the businesses as well as local artisans. It has changed the way business is done and transacted by providing a global marketplace. Ecommerce present a great marketing platform to the domestically produced products (Aitha, K.R, 2012). It provides opportunities to the exporters for the expansion of their business. As exports are a major source of income for the handicraft manufacturers and marketers this gives them a new opportunity to increase their sales & market coverage.

The much-widened gap between artisanal clusters in India and the potential market is covered by ecommerce websites such as:

- **Unravelindia.com:** Apparel, home furnishing, etc
- **Karigar.com:** furniture, apparel, etc.
- **Fiber2fashion.com:** men and women Apparels, accessories, etc
- **Fabindia.com:** Men and women Apparels, beauty products, accessories, etc.
- **Buyjharcraft.com:** Silk sarees, bamboo furnishing, beauty products, home décor, men apparel, etc.
- **Flipkart.com:** Books, mobile phones, digital cameras, laptops, watches, clothing and other products.
- **Limeroad.com:** branded clothing, shoes, handbags, watches, home décor, accessories
- **Ebay.com:** Consumer electronics products, fashion apparel, sporting goods, etc.

For tech savvy buyers online is the easiest way to find and shop for various handicrafts. Also ecommerce is one of the most promising channels in today's marketing scenario for selling handicrafts. It makes sure the easy availability of goods at global level. E-tailing is gaining

ground. In the year 2012, clothing and apparel segment clocked online revenues to the tune of \$ 19.5 billion (T. Taylor, E.D.E. Owusu, 2012). Online retailing is classified into three main categories:

1. Business to Consumer (B2C) – Here an enterprise sell handicrafts directly to the consumer. For examples Amazon.com
2. Business-to-Business (B2B) – Here enterprises increase the sale of their wholesale products and such B2B websites are for manufacturers and suppliers of different products. For examples Alibaba.com
3. Business to government (B2G) – B2G refers to those E-commerce transactions through which business enterprises sell to government. Here business houses directly deal with government offices.

India's cultural diversity provides remarkable art and craft products. Total worth of the Indian handicraft industry across the globe is US \$ 100 billion (SunDaram I. S., 2012). In the world's handicraft, market share of India is 2%. Carpets, wood ware, bamboo products, marble sculpture, bronze sculpture, leather products, paintings, zari goods, embroidered goods and jewelry are few of the most desired handicraft products from India. Rising demand of Indian handicrafts in US, Britain, Canada, Germany, Italy etc provide great opportunity. Each industry need handicraft such as fashion industry, real estate, home décor etc.

The Internet will be more important if you are conducting B2B eCommerce. As trade between e-tailing businesses moves online, so all the processes and services that support this trade, such as logistics and document management, also has to move online. E-tailing can help small enterprises maximise both internal and external efficiencies (e.g., filling excess transport capacity). Electronic networks may also open up new ways of managing the supply chain (e.g., cutting down on paperwork and speeding up communications), allowing streamlining of business operations, reducing costs and improving efficiency.

Necessity of e-tailing of handicraft

India's handloom/craft sector is a RS 24,300 crore industry with more than 13 million artisans, half of which are disbursed across 24,000 co-ops averaging a hundred members each. Lets understand how margins are distributed to key players at the per unit level. In the handicraft sector, artisans acquire raw materials for RS 100, by using their skills they create a finished good, and then sell them to traders for RS 110-120. The finished good is sold through multiple layers of traders until distributors and retailers at the end of the supply chain

purchase it for RS 160-180. The final price of the product for the consumers is around RS 250 to 300. As a result, in the current supply chain, inefficient intermediaries in aggregate receive a margin of 150-200%. However, producers are seeing only 10-20% profit margins. Further, producers often have to borrow funds to purchase raw materials, impacting margins and/or locking them into unscrupulous distributors who finance their materials. In addition to challenges associated with pricing, multiple layers of intermediaries insulate producers from consumers, leaving them unable to assess market trends to create differentiated products. Due to lack of differentiation and the control of intermediaries within the supply chain, artisans are forced to operate in a distorted market where their products are being sold as if they were commodities. E-tailing will help to reduce this margin by eliminating layers of intermediaries or middlemen.

E-tailing platform provide co-ops and producers the ability to list and sell their products to larger markets to realize a better price. Through this platform, regional and national marketplaces connect producers to complimentary suppliers, co-ops and wholesale distributors, along with new B2B and B2C opportunities. In the handloom sector for example, this platform enables the following supply chain linkages to occur:

- Processed cotton is procured by Spinning Co-op mills to process and create yarn
- Yarn is pre-processed in Dyeing units
- Designers and other organizations provides designs to Weavers or Co-ops
- Handloom Weavers/Co-ops produce fabric as per the designs
- Traders, Retailers, Exporters procure fabrics from Co-ops or weavers
- Local and regional garment manufacturers and consumers buy the fabrics

In addition to more control over margins, these linkages give producers the chance to interact with the market directly. This provides an understanding of what customers want and the ability to create differentiated products that will fetch a premium margin.

Advantages of e-tailing in handicrafts marketing:

E-tailing offers unique advantages to the consumer that no other form of retailing can match for selling of handicrafts. Reasons for e-tailing coming up as a hot avenue in the handicraft retail sector can be attributed to multiple factors such as:

Minimal investment - E-tailing does not require a retailer to invest in warehouses, showrooms or other commercial properties at prime locations. Handicraft retailers operate

through their web sites and thus save drastically on the real estate costs. The real estate costs in the metropolitan cities can be prohibitively high. Moreover, maintenance costs of a virtual handicraft store are negligible in comparison to a physical handicraft store.

Comfortable and easy to use - The Internet offers easy and comfortable access to all customers irrespective of their location. Over the Internet, respective regional handicraft product information is just a few clicks away, easily accessible from the comfort of a home. Traditional retailing is quite cumbersome in contrast to E-tailing. It involves agitated search for the required product, running up and down the retail store, asking the poorly trained store assistants for help. The process involves significant wastage of valuable time. Simply put, shopping on the Internet for fifteen minutes is equivalent to a two-hour trip to the regional market. Consumers prefer to save their precious time so that they can better utilize it.

Customer interaction - The greatest benefit of e-tailing is its ability to interact with the customers. Such an interaction allows the retailers to reach the individual customers and react appropriately to their responses. This allows customers to get their customized handicraft requirement. Interaction acts as a vital tool for mass customization. This has also led to greater satisfaction among the online buyers.

Mass Media - A supermarket is limited in its area of operation. It caters to a specific geographical location such as a city and/or its suburbs. However, a web site is globally accessible leading to a worldwide reach and an increased potential customer base. For example a customer of Rajasthan can purchase Jharkhand's silk saree over internet.

Search option - With web search capabilities (which need further development) it is easier to find the particular types of goods required by a customer.

Consumer empowerment -The consumer decides what he wants to buy rather than the retailer offering what he wants to sell. This ultimately translates into.

User friendly – Handicraft web portals are designed in such a way that customer can make online purchase of handicrafts without any difficulty. Customers can execute transactions via the same medium the information is provided, so there is no disconnect between the desire to purchase and the ability to purchase. (Payment schemes are still evolving and therefore this advantage is likely to become more apparent in the future.)

Effective price discrimination - E-tailers can use price discrimination of handmade products in an effective and efficient manner. E-tailers can use previous transactions to identify the likelihood of products being purchased at certain price points and use this information for price discrimination.

Customized product placement - E-tailers can change the online placement/display of a product based on the previous transactions so as to increase the visibility of handicraft that the user is more likely to buy based on the previous encounter at the time purchase. This allows a contextual design of placement to ensure conversion of a visit/hit to the handicraft web portals into a sale of desired handicraft.

Global reach - Customers have a much wider choice at their fingertips (a variety of handicraft web portals to choose from etc.) In this way, the web creates a global market place that brings together multiple consumers and retailers.

Benefits offered by Online Medium

To customers	To business
Convenience- If the products are delivered at home by handicraft marketers this would increase the convenience for the customers. The home delivery is generally free of cost.	Wider reach- Handicraft web portals has a wider reach since the website can be accessed anywhere.
Discounts- Since e-tailing eliminates middlemen, a major chunk of savings can be passed on to customers via discounts and it will also help artisans to enjoy increased margins.	Better targeting- There can be different segments of handicraft lover’s i.e. elite group of customers, middle class, upper middle class. Businesses can devise their strategies to target specific segment of customers of handicrafts.
More variety- The different varieties of products are displayed in a better manner through websites. The goods are arranged category wise i.e. home décor, furnishing, accessories, apparel, etc. The customers can easily choose from them.	Focus on core competencies- Instead of investing time and money in showrooms or warehouses handicraft marketers can focus on the core competencies that would enhance their business. E-tailing provides these benefits.

Challenges for e-tailing in handicrafts marketing

Most of the e-tailing ventures of handicrafts have not been as profitable as they were expected to be, the primary reasons were:

Security issues - Security issues hold the center stage when it comes to consumer concerns while shopping handmade products through the online media. A lack of trust and privacy concerns prevents a lot of consumers from making online purchases. Consumers are also concerned with the use of their personal data provided during the online transactions.

Customer retention - Most of the people buying on the Internet do so out of curiosity and this makes a repeat purchase highly unlikely. If customer is not satisfied through his first experience of online purchase of handmade products he will not make a repeat purchase.

Unsuitable for certain product categories – In case of product categories that require relatively higher customer involvement, the e-tailing route is found to be grossly inadequate in providing sufficient information to the customers. Examples include retailing of products like handmade clothes, natural cosmetics etc. Most customers are comfortable buying books and music on the Internet because the information required for making these purchases and the customer involvement is low. However, in case of a blue Trouser, the customer may want to know things such as: Which shade of blue is it? How does it feel on the skin? How easily does it crease? The traditional retailing does not suffer from such a problem. In the non-standard product categories, the Internet offers limited amounts of crucial information to the customer. In such cases, only the seller knows about the true quality of the trouser and this leads to an ‘information asymmetry’.

Shopping is still a touch-feel-hear experience - Some do not suffer from 'time-poverty' and shopping is still considered to be a family outing. Hence this type of an environment creates a problem of customer retention.

Complicated medium - Ease of use is a problem, as the web design may suffer from high complexity bordering on total chaos in some cases. The haphazard design of online handicrafts web portals is not user friendly and thus do not result in purchase.

Navigation hiccups - E-tail stores do not have standardized designs in comparison to the physical handicraft retail stores and product catalogs. Therefore different user behaviors (navigation schemes) need to be learned for each handicraft e-tail store. This is a temporary issue as the evolution of the web continues.

Website design flaws - Graphic presentation and aesthetics may not be as compelling for handicraft web portals as in case of a physical retail store or a product catalog. This is a temporary issue that may resolve with the evolution of the web design.

Limited access to the Internet - Not all customers have access to the web, as they do to the postal system. This is a temporary issue as the evolution of the web continues.

Some Tips for Improved Order Fulfillments:

- *Keep the customer informed* – to inform the customer probably via email. This is vitally important and might include: confirming the sale, the expected delivery date and follow-ups to check delivery has been completed. An effective communication in e-tailing will help to establish a relationship of trust with your customers. With e-tailing, many of these functions can be automated using off-the-shelf software.
- *Establish personal contact* – to establish contact with customer by telephone or in person if local. This is crucially important when customers have problems or complaints regarding the product.

Conclusion

E-tailing in India is still in its evolving stage and provides a huge opportunity for e-trailer's because of increasing disposable incomes, more penetration of internet and mobile and the growing consumer awareness of e-tailing. This is a good opportunity for handicraft retailers also as it creates a new opportunity for them with the increasing preferences of handicrafts by customers. Handicraft organizations' need to tap this e-tailing opportunity as it is providing them a new way to increase their market reach. To be successful they also need to target the semi-rural and rural areas. Initiatives by the government and e-tailing companies should be taken to make the supply chain and the payment procedures trouble free. Mobile Apps should be developed to reach more customers. Handicraft producers not having much knowledge in running businesses through e-commerce may go for tie-ups with e-commerce companies like Flipkart, SnapDeal, Amazon, Ebay, etc.

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